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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To devise an engagement strategy that allows for co-creation and user acceptance of solutions and services, it is essential to map out key stakeholders and the related goals, barriers and drivers in the context of each pilot site. Therefore, a methodology that considers community context, engagement objectives and stakeholder mapping has been applied to each pilot site to produce a consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

The starting point of this community engagement methodology is the close collaboration with local pilot partners to understand the needs and challenges of their communities. Through scoping questionnaires and remote interviews, the social backdrop and community context of each pilot location has been taken into consideration, including the infrastructure, composition of users and culture of the specific region. Workshops were conducted with representatives from each pilot to map out the key stakeholders in terms of their interest in the project, and their ability to influence the success of project goals. In addition to investigating the community context, green energy goals and key stakeholders, results from the business and use cases work from WP2 was considered when creating targeted stakeholder engagement activities in the individual pilot locations.

As an output of this community data collection and analysis, the ACCEPT consumer validation and design roadmap has been developed. This strategic plan outlines the recommended engagements to take place within each of the pilot communities throughout the ACCEPT project. These engagements will primarily focus on two objectives: 1) facilitating a co-creation approach for the ACCEPT service design (e.g. persona development and tool feedback) and 2) promoting collaboration with key stakeholders and addressing potential barriers to the adoption of the ACCEPT solution in local communities. Deliverable 7.1 *Consumer Validation Report* will further expand upon the specific co-creation engagements outlined in this deliverable. This roadmap will be flexible over the next 32 months due to changing circumstances and unforeseen developments. However, this roadmap serves as a key reference point to guide citizen engagement and co-creation activities that will go hand-in-hand with the technical ambitions of the ACCEPT project and the goals of the pilot sites.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of task

This deliverable will describe the engagement roadmap for interacting with pilot stakeholders and validating the ACCEPT services design. In addition, the methodology for mapping stakeholders and planning the required engagements will be explained. The stakeholder mapping and engagement goals for each pilot are described and then mapped onto the overall engagement roadmap for the ACCEPT project.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

Chapter 2 describes the methodology for identifying pilot site goals, mapping key stakeholders and planning engagement activities.

Chapter 3 will provide the outcome of the community context and objectives analysis as well as the stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement activity recommendations for the Greek pilot site.

Chapter 4 will provide the outcome of the community context and objectives analysis as well as the stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement activity recommendations for the Spanish pilot site.

Chapter 5 will provide the outcome of the community context and objectives analysis as well as the stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement activity recommendations for the Dutch pilot site.

Chapter 6 will provide the outcome of the community context and objectives analysis as well as the stakeholder mapping and targeted engagement activity recommendations for the Swiss pilot site.

Chapter 7 provides a comprehensive engagement roadmap of all anticipated activities related to pilot site goals and stakeholders as well as ACCEPT solution developments (technical, business models, etc.).

Chapter 8 will summarise the output from the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap, referring to each pilot site. It will also refer to how the work described in D3.7 contributes to the key performance indicators of the living lab activities for T3.1 in WP3.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The consumer engagement and design validation roadmap is related to the living lab activities (WP3: T3.1) and related deliverables (D3.1 and D3.2). The engagements described here will also be linked to the deliverable D7.1 *Consumer Validation Report* in WP7. In addition, the results from the concept survey (D2.1) are utilised here to inform the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

Key insights from D2.1 ACCEPT Business Scenarios, Use Cases & Requirements

As reported in D2.1 *ACCEPT Business Scenarios, Use Cases & Requirements*, a concept testing survey was sent to specific stakeholders and end-users in the pilot communities. The goal of this survey was to collect feedback on the user requirements related to the ACCEPT business and use cases. Also included in this survey were specific questions related to the appeal of the ACCEPT energy community concept (see Figure 1) and the specific role the stakeholder would like to play in such a community (see Figure 2). These results are highly relevant to the consumer engagement planning described in this deliverable as they provide a preliminary measure of how stakeholders and citizens perceive these key concepts and which pilots may be more resistant to them.

The results suggest that the ACCEPT energy community concepts were favourably perceived by most respondents. The Spanish and Greek pilots saw the most positive response to the energy community concept, while the Swiss and Dutch pilots found the concept to be less appealing. However, while the concept survey responses indicated that the community may have hesitations about the ACCEPT energy community concept as it was presented, reports from Hieropgewekt (taken from <https://www.hieropgewekt.nl/lokale-energie-monitor>) show that customers in the Netherlands are generally open to participation in such arrangements. Taken together, this suggests clarification may need to be provided to the community so that they can better align with ACCEPT vision with the existing Dutch culture around energy cooperatives

Regarding interest in active involvement with the project, respondents in Spain, Greece, and the Netherlands were willing to be actively or moderately involved. However, more than half of the Swiss respondents indicated that they would prefer to be only passively involved (i.e. not engaging with any activities). Most of the Netherlands respondents preferred to be moderately involved. Therefore, engagements aimed at identifying the effect of more passive involvement would be beneficial to determine what steps can be taken to increase active involvement if required.

Reaction to energy community concept across pilots

Is the ACCEPT concept of energy communities appealing to you?

Figure 1 Energy community concept appeal (B2C)

End user's preferred level of involvement
As an ACCEPT end-user, what role would you like to play in the energy community?

Figure 2 End-user preferences for their energy community involvement (B2C)

Business model feedback analysis

Analysis of the potential risks and barriers related to the business cases designed within the ACCEPT project (deliverable 2.1) brings some insight into the importance of engaging citizens and residents into the design and as active participants in demand response. Lack of citizen engagement or user drop-out were seen almost universally as a risk across the different pilot sites, an observation that is in line with the interviews done by GECO with the pilot partners. Most business cases require that consumers or prosumers change their energy consumption behaviour for them to become economically viable. Transparency and clear communication and guidance to end-users might also help to avoid any trust issues, especially related to data management for privacy. Other barriers potentially relevant to the engagement activities include an unsupportive legislative framework in some of the countries for forming energy communities or engaging in energy prosumer activities. In addition, some of the business models might result in a conflict of interest between different stakeholders, for example, increased local energy production might result in lower revenue for a DSO. Key findings of the concept survey (D2.1) has been utilized also to inform the chapters on individual pilot sites in this document.

2. Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap: Methodology

2.1. Methodology

This chapter will outline the high-level framework for determining the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap. This framework is then applied to each pilot site to determine a strategic roadmap (see Chapters 3-6).

To effectively outline a consumer engagement and design validation roadmap and ensure the right stakeholders are interacted with at each pilot site, it is important to utilize a standardized framework for investigating community context, key stakeholders and pilot site objectives. Figure 3 display an overview of this framework.

Figure 3 Methodology for creating the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap

Community context and objectives

The goal of investigating the community context is to understand the larger environment in which the pilot site resides and to specify the core objectives of the pilot community. The community contextualization determines what the community's ambitions are related to the green energy transition and what social, cultural, or technical factors might impact these goals. Through investigating these critical questions, the ACCEPT project is better positioned to identify key community and stakeholder groups and determine appropriate engagement tasks.

When developing a service to be deployed in a community, it is important to understand the regional context. This includes detailing the types of local businesses and residential buildings in the area. It is also important to identify the regional ethnography and the related opportunities and barriers this may bring for integrating the ACCEPT solution. With regards to the community objectives, whilst goals across pilots in the ACCEPT project will inevitably share similarities, there may also be nuances due to specific regional or pilot site characteristics. Therefore, it is important to determine the community objectives from the perspective of the pilot site representatives.

To gather these details on community objectives and local stakeholders, a pilot site questionnaire (Appendix A) and a follow-up interview (Appendix B) was conducted with the ACCEPT pilot leaders. The questionnaire requires partners to summarize their pilot goals and in which aspects of the piloting, they would like to involve community stakeholders. The interview allowed for a follow-up discussion to elaborate and update information gathered from the initial scoping survey. As described in D3.1, this questionnaire and interview formed part of the 'bottom-up' process in the living lab hybrid collaboration approach (Figure 4). Ultimately, the bottom-up perspective will be aligned with the 'top-down' inputs ascertained from the ACCEPT project coordination and technical team to provide an overall engagement roadmap (further explained in Chapter 7).

Figure 4 ACCEP Hybrid Collaboration Approach

Community stakeholder mapping

As an output of the community contextualization, the key stakeholders in each pilot were identified by the pilot representatives. A community stakeholder matrix mapping analysis based on Mendelow (1991) was then undertaken to determine the role each stakeholder has concerning the ACCEP project (see Figure 5). This type of analysis considers stakeholders along the dimensions of *interest* and *influence*. Interest is related to how motivated the stakeholder would be to participate or follow the project. Influence refers to the extent to which the stakeholder can control or influence factors related to the project’s success. Considering stakeholders along these dimensions can guide pilot representatives on what type of relationship is required between themselves and the various local stakeholders as well as the type of engagement activities required when interacting with stakeholders. This matrix is used as a guide for pilot partners to consider stakeholders in terms of interest and influence. However, it is only a guide, the descriptions in Figure 5 of how to interact with stakeholders is not a rigid set of rules. For example, if a stakeholder resides in the ‘inform’ section of Mendelow’s (1991) matrix, it does not mean they cannot be consulted. In addition, if no stakeholders reside in the ‘involve’ sector of the matrix, it does not mean no one will be involved in the pilot engagement activities. What can be interpreted from the segment in which a stakeholder resides is their level of importance. Because the ‘collaborate’ segment is at the higher end of both the interest and influence dimensions, if a stakeholder resides in this segment, it can be concluded that they are of high importance. The ‘involve’ and ‘consult’ quadrants are important for either influence or interest, respectively, but not both. Those in the ‘inform’ segment are relatively low on both interest and influence dimensions. However, this does not mean ‘inform’ stakeholders are not important, furthermore, stakeholders can often change move along these dimensions depending on contextual changes and project developments.

Figure 5 Mendelow's (1991) stakeholder mapping matrix

Building on the information gathered from the pilot scoping questionnaire, a stakeholder mapping workshop was conducted with each pilot partner (Appendix C). Within this workshop, pilot representatives carried out two tasks. Firstly, they were asked to explain why they identified particular stakeholders as key to the ACCEPT project. Secondly, they were asked to place each stakeholder on the interest/influence matrix. As an output of this remote workshop, a collective understanding of each pilot community's anticipated roles of the key stakeholders was achieved.

Targeted engagement activity recommendations

With the community objectives and stakeholder mapping completed for each pilot site, targeted engagements required at each pilot site can be recommended. These targeted engagements will serve a variety of functions, such as educating or informing citizens, facilitating co-creation, relationship building and identifying barriers and drivers related to the ACCEPT solutions, to name but a few. The recommended engagements will be directed towards each identified stakeholder, including when they need to be interacted with and the type of interaction required (Table 1 displays an example of a targeted engagement activity recommendation).

Table 1 Example of targeted engagement activity recommendations

SH	When to interact	Type of interaction
Facility manager	M12	Consult/inform

The potential engagements listed in the targeted engagement activity recommendations are derived from pilot partner inputs via the pilot questionnaire and workshops. These suggested engagements need to be validated and discussed with the pilot representative through an iterative process to ensure engagements are carried out efficiently and effectively. Consequently, the engagement roadmap will need to be revised and updated as the project progresses, the engagement details identified at this stage should not be considered rigid. When dealing with a variety of different stakeholders over a long period, factors such as individual needs, regional changes and project developments will impact aspects such as how important a stakeholder is or when the optimum time to

consult with stakeholders will be. Applying flexibility in the engagement plan ensures that engagements are efficient and effective and stakeholder relationships are harmonious and productive.

2.2. COVID Impact

Due to the current Covid-19 pandemic, modifications had to be made to the work carried out for the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap methodology. The main adjustment was substituting the pilot site visits to remote methods, such as utilizing surveys and online interviews when interacting with pilot representatives. This also resulted in a slight delay in the remote methods utilized as there was an element of 'wait and see' to determine if in-person meetings would be possible.

3. Pilot Site Community: Aspra Spitia Community, Greece

3.1. Community context

The area of Aspra Spitia can be considered as a large, tight-knit, all-inclusive community. The area was built to develop into a community. As a result, within the region, there is all the necessary infrastructure, such as commercial buildings and public services, which allows the area and its community to function and thrive.

The self-sufficient nature of this pilot region instils an attitude of self-reliance in the residents and businesses. This attitude is an important factor that coincides with the region's goal of achieving zero emissions by 2050. This larger goal is a driver for the community's participation in ACCEPT, intending to promote a more innovative and forward-thinking approach to energy societies and the energy transition.

The concept survey results which assessed the acceptance of the ACCEPT solutions in Aspra Spitia demonstrate an overall very positive attitude towards the initiative, and most of the community members are willing to become active members in the ongoing pilots. Some of the potential barriers identified include mostly technical barriers, such as concerns related to data management and privacy, followed by concerns over increases in the electricity bill and loss of control over devices. A few respondents also mentioned that the services alone might not be sufficient to meet energy efficiency because the buildings themselves would need improvements in insulation and waterproofing. Many of these concerns can be tackled with resident engagement and education about the solutions.

3.2. Engagement objectives

The main objectives for the Greek pilot include:

- Raising awareness and understanding in the people of the community on relevant energy topics, both relevant to the ACCEPT project and other energy solutions anticipated to be introduced in the future. This will facilitate the integration of these services within the community. In addition, increasing community knowledge on energy will allow them to become better decision-makers and encourage positive sustainable energy habits.
- Increasing customer loyalty and overall satisfaction through the reduction of energy bills. In turn, this will promote a positive brand identity of the energy supplier.
- From a technical perspective, gaining a better view of the profile portfolio.

3.3. Mapping of key stakeholders

Figure 6 shows stakeholder mapping within the interest /influence matrix for the Greek pilot site. Table 2 provides additional details on these stakeholders, including why they are important and how they can be reached.

Figure 6 Aspra Spitia: Stakeholder mapping

Table 2 Aspra Spitia: Stakeholder roles

Collaborate	
Facility managers	These stakeholders can promote the energy transition within their respective buildings. They have a key role as gatekeepers as they have access to citizens and can deliver information for increasing knowledge.
Municipality	The municipality already has a keen interest in the project and have taken part in related meetings/correspondents. They are particularly interested in the work being done in the football stadium. Therefore, it would be beneficial to gather feedback from this motivated stakeholder group. The municipality is not reached directly through the pilot partner, instead, they are engaged via the facility management team. It is important to consider this as a commercial communication and technical information should be kept to a minimum or translated into digestible information/materials.
Involve	
Citizens	Citizens are central to the ACCEPT project. The residential homes within the community are owned by Mytilineos, therefore, the residents already know and

	trust the company. The citizen's current level of interest is in ACCEPT relatively low at the moment, increasing their interest is a key focus for the engagement activities. Engaging and informing citizens early will be crucial for increasing integration of the ACCEPT solution. To this end, an introductory workshop is currently being organized to better inform them about the process and materials that have already been created. In the interest of continued engagement, it will be important to implement feedback loops to frequently share results from user testing of the ACCEPT solution.
Inform	
DSO	It would be of interest to gather feedback (e.g. via a workshop) from the DSO in the final stages of the project to discuss future services and how they could be tested in the market. The current retailer-based solutions are not at a stage where they can be considered market-ready, therefore they are not relevant for the DSO at this stage.
Other industries (e.g. I.T. companies)	There is the potential that in the later development stages of the ACCEPT project that other industries, such as I.T. companies, would be interested in the ACCEPT solutions.

3.4. Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Table 3 displays the planned engagements with the stakeholders in the Greek pilot site.

Table 3 Aspra Spitia: Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction(s)
Facility manager	Early (e.g. M10-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Tools training • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
Municipality	Early contact (e.g. M10-M14), possibly ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Project updates/results share back • Knowledge share on ACCEPT & stadium • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Citizens	Ongoing (e.g. M10-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and bi-yearly workshops • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back
DSO	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop to gather feedback about future services
Other industries	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions

4. Pilot Site Community: Renewable Energy Cooperative Buildings, Spain

4.1. Community context

The Spanish pilot is led by La Solar and MIWenergia. MIWenergia is a relatively new company founded in 2014. They have been involved in other H2020 projects and recruited La Solar for the ACCEPT project. La Solar is a consumer electricity retailer founded 5 years ago that offers renewable energy solutions. They currently have 271 members as part of their co-operative with approximately 1600 electricity contracts. There is a supportive relationship between the two companies which comes from their existing relationship of support and information exchange.

La Solar cooperatives produce energy for mostly family consumption, and 85% of customers are families. They also provide 53 education centres (33 public high schools), which covers 30 % of high schools in the region. In addition, 20 private high schools, and a reduced number of large consumers form part of the cooperative. In ACCEPT, only the residential customers will participate.

Overall, the people involved in the La Solar cooperative are more aware of energy topics than most people. There is a very high level of loyalty with the residential customers and education centres. The cooperative grows slowly, and so far, it does not do publicity but relies on word-of-mouth marketing. While the private residential customers will form a part of the pilot activities, other members may also be engaged. For example, high schools provide an opportunity for educational presentations.

Within the pilot region, other co-operatives play a similar role to that of La Solar. There is an association of these cooperatives and they have a good relationship and share data related to self-consumption.

The most relevant barriers envisaged by the Spanish pilot representatives refer to the application's ease of use. The solution must be easy to use for citizens. It should contain simple messages so they can easily access the demand response actions. This is linked to the limited knowledge of users about energy topics and changes. People will likely not have pre-existing knowledge and will be reliant on the information provided. Therefore, ensuring they receive sufficient explanation is important, so they are aware of what is being achieved and why. In addition, there is a need to develop incentives for end-users to facilitate their participation and solution integration. With regards to the potential barriers within the ACCEPT concept development, some of the use cases involve legislative changes that currently are in the development stage and not yet available. In addition, the aggregators' role in the model is still to be concretely defined.

The concept survey indicates that community members have very positive attitudes towards the initiative, and most of them would be interested in taking part in the project actively. Concerns exist towards adjusting habits if prices change daily and if people have fixed schedules which could interfere with demand response or live on the site only part of the year.

The concept survey investigating perceptions on the business cases show that legal barriers would influence the success of some of the business cases tested. There is a need for clear legislation for energy communities, energy self-consumption policies and peer-to-peer trading policies.

4.2. Engagement objectives

The main objectives for the Spanish pilot include:

- To become forward-thinking thereby setting apart from competitors in the market
- To develop smart technologies to promote the self-consumption model
- To facilitate the incorporation of citizens into the new energy model of prosumers
- To increase awareness and education about the technological innovation associated with the project

4.3. Mapping of key stakeholders

7 shows stakeholder mapping within the interest /influence matrix for the Spanish pilot site. Table 4 provides additional details on these stakeholders, including why they are important and how they can be reached.

Figure 7 LaSolar: Stakeholder mapping

Table 4 LaSolar: Stakeholder roles

Collaborate	
Prosumer/consumer	This is the biggest target group of the pilot site. Consumers and prosumers have a lot to gain from the initiative, and La Solar already has a good relationship with this group. 50 residential customers have been identified to participate in the testing of ACCEPT solution. La Solar plans to increase communication with them. There will be 17 prosumer customers, and possibly more prosumers and citizen retailers could be integrated.
City council	Two city councils have expressed an interest in the ACCEPT project. One already has a contract to establish an energy community. La Solar has established relationships with these two councils. The extent to which the municipalities will engage in the project is yet to be defined.

Involve	
DSO	The DSO is a very important stakeholder, however, DSOs are unlikely to be interested in engaging in the project at this stage. Establishing communication with them is unlikely at present.
Citizen/resident	Dynamic prices will be important to this group. Citizens, in general, can be accessed via city councils and through La Solar's cooperative connections.
Business manager	Interest in energy self-consumption is currently growing. These stakeholders could be interested if they can get more money for contributing to the grid. This stakeholder would need convincing from the financial aspects to be involved in the project.
Consult	
Legislators	The ACCEPT project might not directly engage with legislators. However, potential legislative changes will need to be followed, since the ongoing legislative reforms may influence the project.
Retailer/aggregator/ESCO	Aggregators and retailers may want to get their customers involved in the ACCEPT solutions. The pilot site could engage with ESCOs since they already have some business contacts. La Solar and MIWenergia will provide the retailer perspective at the pilot site.

4.4. Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Table 5 displays the planned engagements with the stakeholders in the Spanish pilot site.

Table 5 LaSolar: Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction
Consumer/ prosumer	Ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Tools training Co-creation activities Project updates/results share back
Municipality	Early (M10-M14), ongoing + maintain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Project updates/results share back
Citizens	Ongoing (e.g. M10-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Prosumer/cooperative outreach Co-creation activities Project updates/results share back
DSO (AEM, Switzerland)	Mid (M15-30)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultation with AEM to exchange experiences on DSO engagement
DSO	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Other industries	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
Aggregator/ ESCO/ Retailer	Ongoing (ESCOs), late (e.g. M37-M42) (retailers, aggregators)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions

Business Managers	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions
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5. Pilot Site Community: Eva Lanxmeer Community, Netherlands

5.1. Community context

The Dutch pilot site is a district that will primarily validate the community aggregator concept. Energie Samen Rivierenland is a regional cooperative and will engage in flexibility service provision as an aggregator to balance the portfolio of the energy provider and for local congestion management for the DSO. The revenues gained will be shared with the prosumers in the district.

The Eva Lanxmeer community in Culemborg is an established sustainable urban demonstration site and community with installed solar roof PV, EV charging stations and grid-tied energy storage system. The community can be characterised as sharing similar values around sustainability, and there are bottom-up initiatives to become more environmentally friendly. The community is keen on increasing the amount of locally produced energy and finding solutions to balance the electric network.

The goals for the pilot site include consuming up to 70% of locally produced energy, balancing supply and demand, and utilising local storage capacity to avoid the congestion of the network. The use of locally produced district heating is also being tested. The goal is to find relevant business cases for the cooperatives.

Some of the potential barriers for engagement include mild resistance to smart meters and wifi from some of the residents.

The concept survey to analyse the pilot communities' perspectives on ACCEPT solutions (see D2.1) indicates a moderate interest from the community members. Some residents are already taking measures to utilise devices in an energy-efficient way. Many express potential fatigue to ongoing community-based projects and fear for lack of time to commit themselves to this project. Indeed, energy-related projects have been ongoing in the community for a long-time and the site has attracted interest at national and international levels. Overall, however, the approach is being seen as beneficial to the community and previous research has shown that customers in the Netherlands are open to the energy community concept (see section 1.3 for more details).

5.2. Engagement objectives

The main objectives for this pilot community include:

- Increasing energy independence
- Avoiding network congestion and using the available local storage capacity
- Utilizing digital solutions to help to achieve and manage the goals
- Finding relevant business cases for the energy cooperative to exploit

5.3. Mapping of key stakeholders

Figure 8 shows stakeholder mapping within the interest /influence matrix for the Dutch pilot site. Table 6 provides additional details on these stakeholders, including why they are important and how they can be reached.

Figure 8 Eva Lanxmeer: Stakeholder mapping

Table 6 Eva Lanxmeer: Stakeholder roles

Collaborate	
Flex-market supplier (Energie Samen)	This is an important stakeholder for the project who has a high influence on its success. They are also a full partner in ACCEPT.
Coop platform (Energie Samen Rivierenland)	The coop platform would be the one to decide which services to develop for the app.
Residents	Residents are an important stakeholder group and they are likely to have an interest in joining the project. Most of them are prosumers. Co-creation with the residents would be the ideal situation. Residents can be possibly recruited for example through the local heating company Thermo Bello, since many of the residents are customers of this company, or through a residents' association.
Regional energy company	This is a joint company of energy cooperatives in the Rivierenland region to produce regional sustainable energy. The stakeholder has an interest in the price flexibility, but their overall influence on the project might not be so high. Their involvement would be beneficial.
Consult	

Local energy coop	<p>Vrijstad Energie is a local energy cooperative that provides local energy through solar rooftops, as well as owns some of the assets, such as carpports and loading facilities.</p> <p>There is a need to motivate them to be active in the project, as they are currently not expressing much interest in joining the project. They could be the front office concerning the residents.</p>
Local heating company	<p>The local heating company is a gatekeeper to residential customers. The company is formed by the people of the community and therefore, the community has ownership over the company.</p> <p>Very interested but not too influential.</p>
Inform	
Grid operator	<p>The local grid operator might be interested in the project, especially in learning about its results. For this project, legal issues are of interest or concern. Influence is very low.</p>
EV coop platform	<p>EV coop platform with a car-sharing service, an active user of the EV charging stations in the community. They are likely to have an interest in lowered energy prices. How to capitalize that?</p>

5.4. Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Table 7 displays the planned engagements with the stakeholders in the Dutch pilot site.

Table 7 Eva Lanxmeer: Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction	Recruitment process
Flex market supplier (Energie Samen)	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation activities 	
Local energy cooperative	Early (M12-M14), ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Help with recruiting households Project updates/results share back 	
Local heating cooperative	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Help with recruiting households Project updates/results share back 	Existing connections, use them to help to recruit participants
Regional energy company	Early (M12-M14), ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss possibilities around UCs/ BCs for price flexibility 	
Grid operator	Mid, late (M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct engagement to present the project and possibly discuss any legal concerns Project updates/results share back 	

Residents	From Early (M12) and throughout the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro • Tools training • Co-creation activities • Project updates/results share back 	Existing contacts, especially via Thermo Bello and residents' association.
EV coop platform	Early (M12-M14), possibly ongoing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss demand response testing within the charging points • Project updates/results share back 	
Other businesses	Late (e.g. M37-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCEPT 'show and tell' to share results and develop an interest in ACCEPT solutions 	

6. Arena Innovation Community & Fondazione la Sosta, Switzerland

6.1. Community context

Azienda Elettrica di Massango (AEM) is a distribution system operator (DSO) in southern Switzerland. Through the network, it supplies electricity to 9000 users, of which 90 % are residential users. AEM serves three different towns with a mix of high and low population density in the energy distribution area. AEM has started to have more focus on innovation, and they are now participating in H2020 projects. One aim is to investigate possibilities towards self-consumption energy community strategies to optimize local energy production/consumption and stay competitive in the future.

Being a small operator, AEM has a close relationship with the customers, which distinguishes them from other DSOs. This close customer relationship was already leveraged during the data collection for the UC concept test survey (see D2.1) as the pilot partner was able to arrange in-person meetings to describe in detail the meaning of each service and collect customer feedback.

The ACCEPT solution will be tested in the residential district of the Arena Innovation Community and in the elderly care home Fondazione La Sosta, which consist overall of around 50 flats and single houses. AEM estimates that the ACCEPT system could bring minor savings to the tariffs and value to the community through making customers' homes smarter with smart electricity consumption measuring apps and increased transparency towards energy consumption.

Estimated barriers for success are primarily related to citizen acceptance and the effectiveness of the ACCEPT APP. The focus on the successful development of the APP is to avoid the risk of introducing an APP that is not suitable for end-users. In general, citizens in the community are willing to accept new technologies. However, citizens may be unwilling to adjust their behaviour towards the use of devices as they fear losing control of their home appliances. Therefore, citizens need to be educated in the function and processes of demand response, as well as its benefits for a greener society.

Equally, the results of a survey to test the acceptance of ACCEPT tools within the pilot communities indicate that while there is a positive attitude towards the solutions, the community members would like to play only a moderate or passive role related to the activities provided. Considering all this, attention should be paid to the engagement of citizens and providing them information on the possible benefits of demand response initiatives.

From the technical perspective, energy communities require energy storage options which are still expensive, and financially sustainable business models are still to be tested. Related to business models, there are likely to be conflicts of interest between the DSO and other actors, since using local energy might mean less electricity bought from the DSO. Finding business models that are beneficial for both citizens and the DSO or which help to tackle the high capital costs, for example setting up energy storage, would be beneficial.

6.2. Engagement objectives

The main engagement for the Swiss pilot community include:

- Understand the extent to which citizens are willing to adapt their energy consumption behaviour, i.e., social acceptance for demand response
- Understanding the impact of the project on the citizen behaviour
- Developing sustainable business models around energy communities and demand response.

6.3. Mapping of key stakeholders

Figure 9 shows stakeholder mapping within the interest /influence matrix for the Swiss pilot site. Table 8 provides additional details on these stakeholders, including why they are important and how they can be reached.

Figure 9 Swiss pilot: Stakeholder mapping

Table 8 Swiss pilot: Stakeholder roles

Collaborate	
DSO	AEM is an electricity distributor supplying energy to the community. It has a high interest because the project aligns with their business strategy. Equally, influence is high because the customers know them, and they have a good reputation amongst them. AEM has an interest and a reputation for innovation.
Building owner/manager	Building owners and managers transfer the cost of electricity to end-user, but there is some value for building owners in participating in demand response initiatives as their involvement in this green energy research may benefit the reputation of the building. It is something they can use to promote/market the apartments. Building managers are a gatekeeper for success. If the building owner doesn't want to participate, they won't pass the information along to the tenants. In the past, AEM did a two-step process to approach them. First a workshop with the building owners, then a second workshop with tenants.
Municipality	All municipalities are interested in their communities becoming greener. AEM has done a previous project with the municipality and won an award for being the most innovative town in Switzerland. There is existing cooperation and provision of infrastructure: for example, the municipality is the one funding the PV panels being put on the rooftop. The municipality will also provide physical space for workshops. Would need their approval for charging stations.

Public institutions	Some public institutions will be part of the pilot activities of the project. They can be approached through and in collaboration with the Municipality but may require additional specific engagements to be involved in the project. E.g. public pool, soccer field and the elderly care home. The institutions that take part in the pilot program will have a high influence.
Involve	
Pilot site tenants and citizens	<p>Tenants and citizens in the actual pilot site are an important group since they will receive and use the electricity and the success of the project depends on their participation. Need to have a high level of collaboration. The energy transition works if there is awareness amongst the end-users about the importance of demand response.</p> <p>Their interest varies a lot, from middle to low. Some users are very excited about the project, others were very sceptical.</p> <p>An existing good relationship with AEM.</p>
Consult	
Regulators	Likely to be consulted during the project regarding solutions.
Inform	
Citizens	Citizens, in general, may have some interest in the project and the solutions provided. The engagement activities directed to them may include newsletters and other general information distribution. Their impact on the project is likely to be minimal.

6.4. Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Table 9 displays the planned engagements with the stakeholders in the Swiss pilot site.

Table 9 Swiss pilot: Targeted engagement activity recommendations

Stakeholder	When to interact	Type of interaction	Recruitment process
Building owners/ managers	Early (M12-M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Engage individually with each of the building owners Project updates/results share back 	Existing relations
Municipality	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Constant communication (ie. Coordinating the use of workshop spaces etc.) Project updates/results share back 	Existing relations
Pilot site tenants/ citizens/ homeowners	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome workshop/ACCEPT intro Tools training Co-creation activities Project updates/results share back 	Relations are already established through building managers and direct contacts.

Citizens in general	Throughout the project (M12-M42)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project updates/results share back 	
Other industries (e.g. TSO, ESCOs)	Mid to end of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Project results info/share back 	TBA

7. ACCEPT comprehensive engagement roadmap

Chapters 3-6 have outlined the targeted engagement activities for each pilot site. However, it is important to consider these pilot specific engagement activities in the broader context of the overall engagement roadmap for the ACCEPT project. Table 10 provides a comprehensive overview of all engagement activities, including those related to concept testing, business model validation, etc. From the targeted engagement activity recommendation tables in the previous chapters, it is apparent that many engagement activities are common across all pilot sites, such as the welcome/ACCEPT introduction workshops. These common activities are highlighted in blue in Table 10, The targeted engagement activities that are unique to a particular pilot site are highlighted in green.

The planned engagements listed in Table 10 are a result of a comprehensive assessment undertaken with all pilot partners. The suggested engagements have also been initially validated by representatives from each pilot region. However, these listed activities should be considered as planned engagements. The activities and timelines are subject to change depending on project developments. Furthermore, iteration between organizers of the living lab activities in T3.1 and pilot partners may result in changes to the schedule, such as altering time frames or potentially combining workshops across pilot sites.

Table 10 Comprehensive ACCEPT engagement roadmap

Timeline	Stakeholders	Description	Activity	Related tasks
Stage 1: User requirements exploration				
M6	External & internal	Collection of market actor and prosumer requirements	Concept test survey	T2.1
M6-14	External & internal	Pilot welcome workshops/ACCEPT introduction event	Workshops	T3.1, T7.1, T3.4
M10	Internal	Feedback per pilot site on Business Cases-Use Cases-System Architecture and Measurement & Verification Methodology	Survey	T2.2, T2.3
M10-12	External	ACCEPT community member concept test results share back	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1
M10-42	External	[GREEK pilot] – knowledge share with the municipality on ACCEPT and local football stadium	Consultation	T3.4
M10-42	External	[SPANISH pilot] – Outreach activities aimed at consumers and prosumers	Communication/ dissemination	T3.4
M12-14	Internal & external	[DUTCH pilot] – Recruitment of households through local energy & heating cooperative	Consultations and communication	T3.4 & T6.1
M12-14	Internal & external	[DUTCH pilot] – Direct engagement to introduce the project and discuss possibilities around UCs/ BCs for price flexibility with the regional energy company, and to discuss demand response testing	Consultations	T3.4, T2.1

		within the charging points with the EV cooperative platform		
M12-14	External	[SWISS pilot] – Engage individually with each of the building owners	Consultations and communication	T3.4
M12-42	External	Project results shareback with all interested stakeholders	Communication/ dissemination	T3.4, T9.1
M12-15	External & internal	Feedback on Service Level Agreements and contract terms for the business models and services	Survey	T2.5
M12-42	External	[SWISS pilot] – Continued communication with municipality for coordination purposes	Consultations and communication	T3.4
Stage 2: Prototyping validation				
M10-13	External & internal	Participation in ex-ante pilot surveys	Audit	T6.1
M11-12	External	ACCEPT introduction for community members	One page newsletter or community presentation	T3.1, T7.1
M13-14	External	ACCEPT persona validation workshop	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T3.1, T3.4
M15-16	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 1: Feedback on ACCEPT system 1 st prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5
M15-20	Internal	[SPANISH pilot] – consultation with AEM to investigate DSO perspective	Interview	T3.4
M16-M18	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 1 st prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
M18-M21	Internal	Feedback of pre-validation results	TBD	T6.4
M20-24 M15-M23	External	Scheduling of installation activities and training of pilot participants	TBD	T6.5, T6.6
M26-27	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 2: Feedback on ACCEPT system 2 nd prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8
M28-M30	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 2 nd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1

M35-36	External & internal	Co-creation workshop 3: Feedback on ACCEOT system final prototype	4 workshops (one/pilot)*	T7.1, T6.2, WP7, WP8
M37-M39	External	Community co-creation share back: Highlevel insights from 3 rd prototype co-creation workshop	One page newsletter or community presentation	T7.1
Stage 3: Business modelling validation				
M27-M33	External & internal	Feedback on obstacles for DR application in energy communities	TBD	T8.1
M37-40	External	Feedback on business models	TBD	T8.4
M37-M42	External & internal	Sharing of ACCEOT results with businesses	TBD	T3.4
M37-42	External	[GREEK pilot] – consultation with DSO to discuss future services	Interview	T3.4
M37-42	External	[DUTCH pilot] – direct engagement with Grid operator to present the project and discuss any legal concerns	Interview	T3.4
M37-M42	External	Feedback on exploitable results & business potential	TBD	T8.2

*Note: Budget allocated for local language moderation

8. Summary and conclusions

Through the methodology outline in chapter 2, a consumer engagement and design validation roadmap has been created. This roadmap combines the project goals with individual pilot site needs with regards to the stakeholder engagements. This deliverable has described the key elements and procedures undertaken to effectively map stakeholders and plan targeted engagements at each pilot site. From the scoping survey and interview, the individual context and goals for each pilot have been considered in the mapping of stakeholders and planning of engagements needed for the successful deployment of the ACCEPT services. Through the pilot workshops, key stakeholders have been identified and mapped in a matrix that accounts for each stakeholder’s interest and influence towards the project goals. Ultimately, the contextualization and stakeholder mapping have allowed for the targeted engagement activities to be mapped out in each pilot. Table 11 summarizes the key findings from each pilot assessment in chapters 3-6.

Table 11. Summary of pilot assessments in the consumer engagement and design validation roadmap

Pilot site	Number of objectives	Number of stakeholders and matrix segment	Key stakeholder	Number of potential engagements
Greece	3	3 collaborate 1 involve 2 inform 6 total	Facility managers – these stakeholders are the ‘gatekeepers’ to interacting with the citizens	13
Spain	4	2 collaborate 4 involve 1 consult 7 total	Consumers and prosumers are integral as they have a good relationship with La Solar and MIWenergia and also have the most to gain from the ACCEPT initiative	15
Netherlands	4	4 collaborate 2 consult 2 inform 8 total	The cooperative platform are key as they decide the services which will be part of the APP	17
Switzerland	3	4 collaborate 1 involve 1 consult 1 inform	The DSO is a key stakeholder as the project goals align with their business strategy and the DSO in the region has a good reputation amongst the citizens	13

The engagements highlighted in this document can also be placed in the context of the goals and KPIs related to the living lab engagement activities in T3.1 of WP3. The DoA specifies that 16 workshops (4 in each pilot) will take place as part of the living lab activities. In addition, 700 stakeholders will be directly involved in the piloting activities, and 1000 involved in the co-creation process (see Table 12). As shown in Table 10 in chapter 7, many activities for co-creation such as workshops intended for prototype testing and validating the customer personas, are planned which will result in engaging many stakeholders across all pilot types. These engagements will contribute to meeting the targets outlined in Table 12.

Table 12. KPIs related to the living lab activities (T3.1)

Category	KPI	Metric	Target
Engagement	Stakeholder engagement	Engaging citizens in the demonstration activities	700
		Engaging stakeholders in the co-creation process	1000

9. References

Mendelow, A. (1991). Stakeholder mapping. In Proceedings of the 2nd international conference on information systems, Cambridge, MA.

10. Appendix

10.1. Appendix A: Pilot site questionnaire

Pilot Site Questionnaire

Pilot Partner:

The goals of this questionnaire are to help us understand:

- What you, the pilot partner/leader, wants to achieve in this project
- Which stakeholders we need to involve in the co-creation process to improve the ACCEPT services and products being developed at your pilot site

A few things to keep in mind:

- Think of this as a brainstorming exercise to get the conversation started. We know it's very early in the project and that is very likely that this information may change over time. Your answers today will offer us a useful starting point so we can start working in the right direction.
- Your answers don't have to be long (bullet points are welcome).
- If your answers differ per use case, please specify which use case you are referring to in your responses in ALL questions or you can send back multiple questionnaires if you feel it is clearer.

Stakeholders

A major part of the co-creation process in the living labs process are the stakeholders needed for providing input and feedback. Therefore, the table below is a high-level categorisation of potential stakeholders to guide your thoughts. When answering the following questions, please try to think of all the categories below and be as precise as possible as the purpose of the stakeholder engagement will be multi-fold. For instance, it will not be enough to say "Customers" as stakeholders, but try to explain who is the customer, is it a household, an office building, a solar plant, a power plant, a DSO? Also keep in mind that this is not an exhaustive list, so please don't be restricted only to these stakeholder categories.

Stakeholders	
Project affiliation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal • External
Categories	Energy Sector <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retailers • Aggregator

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSO • TSO • ESCO • Technology provider • Regulator <p>End users</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen/Building resident • Building manager • Facility managers • Business managers • Prosumers/Consumers <p>Facilitators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research/Academic institute • EU Institutions (EC, EU science foundation) • National public authorities (industrial committees, municipalities) • Related EU projects • Organisations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT • EU technology platforms and respective clusters • Public bodies and environmental organisations
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Questions

1. What are your primary goals for your pilot site? What do you want to achieve? What would you consider a successful outcome?
2. Using the table below, please state in which aspects of your pilot would you like to involve external stakeholders that are not part of the consortium (e.g. to discuss new business models, feedback on the product features, market appetite for the services you are testing, to understand drivers and barriers to their adoption, etc.)

Stakeholder category	Briefly describe how you would like them to be involved

3. What other types of customers (other than the ones serviced in your pilot) would be serviced if taken to the market phase?

4. Any other stakeholders you would like to consider in the living lab activities?

10.2. Appendix B: Pilot interview discussion guide

Introduction

- Welcome and introductions
- “In this interview we want to understand how ACCEPT works in your pilot region. Normally we would have a site visit and have a chance to meet up and walk around your pilot region and chat etc., with that not possible in the current covid situation, we have to do this remotely, but try think of this discussion as a substitute for that site visit.
- During this discussion we would like to cover topics on:
 - A broad description/summary of your pilot site – we would like to hear who you are and your role and a bit of detail on your pilot site that’s beyond the GA
 - What *your* goals are with the ACCEPT project
 - Who the key and supporting SHs are related to your goals – and discuss how you want to engage with these different SHs, the process for approaching and interacting with SHs – are they part of your community/network etc.?
- We would like to record this session, for research purpose only, transcript and recordings will not be circulated. Are you ok with this?”

Interviewee profile [community context]

“We can start with you giving us a bit of context and explaining who you are.”

- Tell us a bit about yourself/your company
 - What does your company do?
 - What is the size of your company?
 - Tell us about your role
 - How long have you worked at _____?
- Why did you decide to join the ACCEPT project?
- Tell us about your pilot area
 - What is there mainly residential/business
 - How large is the area
 - Any specific culture or community type in the area

Demo site goals [engagement objectives]

- “Now we have a bit of background information on your pilot site, we’d like to discuss some of the goals that you identified in the demo questionnaire you filled out for us earlier in the year
- To do this I’d like to share my screen”

[open relevant ppt and share screen]

- These are the main goals you identified in the demo questionnaire
 - Would you like to briefly explain / summarise the goals in your own words
 - You can also explain if these goals changed or developed since you responded to our demo questionnaire.

Exploratory questions [community context & community analysis]

“Ok, for the next part of this discussion, we would like to discuss in a bit more detail how your goals fit with the ACCEPT solution.

I will leave these goals on screen so they can be referred to if needed - such as if the barriers vary depending on the type of goal”

- What value, or potential value, is ACCEPT bringing to your community in your area?
- What are the most relevant barriers to the ACCEPT solution that you can envisage?
 - Do these differ depending on the goals you have outlined here?
- How would you describe the costs of implementing the solution (time/personnel)?
- Can you name the most important needs that motivate you to invest time & resources into ACCEPT?
- Are there any risks that you can envisage for implementing the ACCEPT solutions?
- Are other local companies involved or interested in the ACCEPT project?
 - Does your company interact with other groups/companies in your pilot region
 - If so how do you interact, formal/ informal meetings? How often do you meet?

10.3. Appendix C: Discussion guide for stakeholder mapping workshop

Stakeholders [mapping of SHs & engagement strategy]

In this part of the discussion, we would like to map the important stakeholders related to your goals, which you identified in the demo questionnaire.

What we would like to go through each of these one by one – I'll bring it into the middle and you can then give us a brief summary of why you identified them, why they are important and ask you some questions and place them on the interest x influence map,. Lets start with X...

[go through each SH]

- Why did you identify X – why are they important?
- **What kind of interaction** do you foresee with them? Would you like to collaborate closely with them and co-develop for example, or would you like to consult them, perhaps gather feedback on a BM
- **How would you recruit** these SHs, are they part of your existing network?
- **When would you like to talk them**, early in the project? Or perhaps after a specific technical development in advance?
- Finally we would like you to place the SH on the interest x influence axes we have here:
 - Interest is related to how motivated the stakeholder would be in participating in the project
 - Influence refers to the extent to which the SH can control, or influence, factors related to the project and the projects success

Wrap-up

Finally, we will finish up by giving you an explanation of why we are doing this and what the information is used for

- Debrief
 - Information gathered here will contribute to T3.4 & D3.7, as well as other engagement related tasks, WP3 and T7.1 – it helps us to map out the SHs that
 - This is a starting point for us to work together and plan so we can carry out the required engagements
 - SH follow up interviews?? (based on what we have talked about here) – process around September
- Thank them for their time